

Diagnosis and resolution of a customer-defined satisfaction issue in automotive user controls

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Abstract

The usability of automotive controls can have a significant impact on the perception of quality of the vehicle and brand, with a subsequent effect on vehicle sales. Customer-derived information points to a lack of satisfaction with current automotive controls, indicating that the affective elements of interaction are not sufficiently considered during the design phase. This paper presents a case study in which a UK-based vehicle manufacturer became aware of a control usability problem affecting two vehicle lines which was defined by customer-derived data. A measurement study was undertaken which highlighted issues with elements of the existing product characteristics and ergonomic design. The relationship between design targets and product performance is discussed with reference to the suitability of specifications to deliver customer satisfaction and methods for utilizing subjective and objective data to generate engineering specifications are explored.

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Introduction

In recent years, the drive for automotive quality has increasingly focused on the interior of the vehicle, with a corresponding acknowledgement of the influence of perceived quality on the brand as a whole (Kalogerdis, 2004). This approach transcends the bounds of traditional 'quality' metrics, such as durability and fit and finish, to include wider elements of the product experience and its emotional impact on the user (Zeithaml, 1988). From the perspective of the driver, the primary point of interaction with the product is the driver controls and the nature of this interface must be carefully considered to optimise the user experience. Indeed, it is believed that automotive user controls are not currently designed to maximise user satisfaction (Norman, 2004), a problem which will be exacerbated by the influx of new technologies into the car (Stutts et al, 2001). The fundamental challenge is to understand what the user wants and to use that information to generate quantifiable engineering targets, as when this process does not function effectively the quality of the product invariably suffers.

Using suitable methods to collect data at a level which can be applied to the problem is vital. A survey of 61 automotive industry senior executives revealed that the biggest obstacle in collecting better customer information was 'Poor information capture and exchange' (Oracle, 2004). The main source of customer information cited in this survey was 'Commercial market research' – aftermarket data from a third party. The largest such information provider is JD Power & Associates, who have been collecting and interpreting automotive user satisfaction data since the early 1970s. The influence JD Power has over the car-buying public is considerable: Hyundai Motor America reportedly saw a 12% increase in sales of its Sonata model after it came top of its class in a JD Power survey (Palmeri, 2004). JD Power's own data indicate an average 44% sales increase over a 5 year period for manufacturers which achieve a 'High' satisfaction rating (JD Power, 2006a). The effect on sales based on the results from such studies means that they are treated with great importance by automotive manufacturers. Data from the 2006 JD Power IQS indicate that problems related to the usability of user controls have a significant negative impact on the perceived quality of the vehicle as a whole, with a corresponding negative effect on future sales (Howard, 2006).

A commonly-cited example of a poorly-implemented automotive control system is the BMW iDrive. Since its introduction in 2001 on the flagship 7-Series and despite subsequent modifications to improve usability in 2003 and 2006, the system continues to attract negative reviews due to its complexity and lack of intuitiveness from both consumer reviewers (Cobb, 2002; Smith, 2002) and usability experts (Nielsen, 2004; Norman, 2004; Wilkinson, 2002). The majority of complaints centre on the number of menu levels and the amount of time the driver is

required to spend looking at the screen and hence not focusing on the primary task of driving – ‘Eyes-off-the-road’ time is known to be strongly correlated with accident probability (Wierwille, 1995). Proponents of the iDrive assert that usability improves beyond the initial learning phase, but with experts estimating a two-week time scale to achieve this (Day, 2004), doubts remain as to the suitability of the interface to an automotive application¹.

The Craftmanship project at WMG, University of Warwick was instigated under the Premium Automotive Research and Development programme to investigate the perception of quality of luxury vehicle interiors. One aspect of the work covered was the touch and feel quality of interior components, including the haptic characteristics of user controls. This led to the establishment of the Craftmanship Haptics Laboratory, an independent research facility dedicated to the assessment of feel quality of automotive switchgear. Over the past 3 years the facility has been involved in projects supporting a number of vehicle OEMs and tier 1 suppliers, both UK-based and international, through design validation, benchmarking and diagnostic activities. To date, the facility has generated over £2.5m in added value to these businesses.

At the heart of the laboratory is TouchStar switch-feel measurement system – a bespoke system for the haptic characterisation of switchgear and controls. TouchStar is marketed by Benchmark Inc, USA and based on technology originally developed by Ford Research, Dearborn, MI, USA.

Figure 1 - The TouchStar Switch Feel Measurement System

¹ For further examples of iDrive usability issues, see The Product Usability Weblog: <http://www.uselog.com/2007/11/bmw-idrive-legendary-usability.html>; <http://www.uselog.com/2007/12/more-bmw-idrive-reviews-evolution-of.html>; and Car Talk: <http://www.cartalk.com/content/features/goodbadugly/bad.html>

The Craftsmanship team were the first recipients of this system and were instrumental in beta-testing the software, providing feedback to the manufacturers to improve accuracy and functionality. The team also developed improved fixturing methods and measurement practices whilst building considerable experience of issues surrounding switch feel quality.

The following case study describes an example of how a problem with satisfaction and usability in automotive user controls was highlighted through customer-derived information and resolved through the use of objective engineering data. Due to confidentiality product and brand names have been omitted.

Case Study

A UK-based manufacturer of premium vehicles became aware of a problem with the usability of the wash-wipe column stalk used on two vehicle lines. When operating the front wipers by moving the stalk up/down, it was apparently very easy for the driver to accidentally activate the rear wiper, which is controlled by pulling the stalk forwards. Evidence for the problem had been gathered from the JD Power IQS 2006 study (JD Power, 2006c), with verbatim comments highlighting the nature of the issue. The issue “Windscreen wiper/washer difficult to use/understand” ranks 4th and 5th most important for the vehicles in question, compared to 10th most important across the industry as a whole (JD Power, 2006b).

The results from JD Power were further supported by comments from the manufacturer’s vehicle evaluation teams and their own customer survey data, collected after 3 months of vehicle ownership. While the drive teams highlighted and reported the problem, the customer comments also indicated a perceived lack of intuitiveness in the operation of the system, for example:

“From the beginning the rear wiper has operated by itself for no reason.”

“Every time I go to turn on the front windshield wipers, the back ones go on. It seems like the whole system’s backwards.”

To resolve the problem, it was necessary to understand the haptic characteristics of the problem component and the differences from comparable components in which the problem did not occur. The manufacturer approached the Craftsmanship team to perform a benchmarking study on a number of column stalks to collect data that could be used to diagnose the issue and create recommendations for improvements to the design.

The study aimed to address the following questions:

1. What are the key differences in haptic characteristics between the ‘Vehicle X’ column stalk and those from comparable vehicles?
2. How does the ‘Vehicle X’ column stalk perform compared to its design specification?
3. How does the ‘Vehicle X’ column stalk perform compared to the manufacturer’s own switch harmony specification?

Method

The TouchStar system can be configured to measure most types of automotive switch gear using either a linear or rotary actuator with modular end effector components. A column stalk measurement uses the rotary measurement unit with an arm attachment which operates the stalk. The mass of the arm is accounted for in the calibration process prior to measurement. Care must be taken in the fixturing of the component under test in order that excessive loads are applied which restrict the movement of the column stalk, and also that the axis of rotation of the RMU is correctly aligned with that of the stalk.

Figure 2 - Column stalk measurement setup

Once the component is fixtured and the relevant parameters set, the system moves the component through its full range, measuring the torque and angle to produce a trace representing the physical characteristics of the device – the units can be converted to linear

force/displacement through simple trigonometry as the length of the actuator arm is known. Both torque and angle are measured as vector quantities. Most of the devices under test featured three switching positions in the up/down orientation, representing the intermittent, 1st and 2nd wiper speeds. All also featured a single switched position in the fore/aft orientation. Examples can be seen in figures 3 and 4 respectively. The force magnitude and displacement (relative to the 'off' position) of each of these peaks were chosen as metrics for comparison between the column stalks.

Figure 3 - Example front wiper measurement curve

Figure 4 - Example rear wiper measurement curve

Results

Tables 1 and 2 show the force and displacement values at the switching points for each of the functions on the column stalks. Note that Vehicle 4 featured a different detent design with one switching point either side of the rest position, hence positive and negative displacement figures.

Force / N						
Direction	Switching point	<i>Vehicle X</i>	Vehicle 1	Vehicle 2	Vehicle 3	Vehicle 4
Front wiper	1	4.74	4.28	4.08	5.92	7.17
	2	5.16	4.78	4.13	6.76	6.85
	3	5.09	5.03	4.65	7.48	-
Rear wiper	1	2.72	4.03	3.95	6.63	7.11

Table 1 - Measured force at switching point

Displacement / mm						
Direction	Switching point	<i>Vehicle X</i>	Vehicle 1	Vehicle 2	Vehicle 3	Vehicle 4
Front wiper	1	6.41	3.40	3.58	3.51	-21.94
	2	20.03	19.05	17.54	15.59	21.25
	3	32.38	35.28	31.34	27.27	-
Rear wiper	1	4.40	4.70	3.93	6.61	8.52

Table 2 - Measured displacement at switching point

Let us consider what happens when the system is operated from the 'off' position. In this case, a force is applied in either the up/down or fore/aft direction and once the switching force is exceeded the function is activated. Table 3 compares the force values for the first front wiper setting with the rear wiper force values. The Rear/Front switching force ratio is the force required to engage the rear wiper divided by the front wiper force described.

Vehicle	Front wiper switching force/N	Rear wiper switching force/N	Rear/Front switching force ratio
Vehicle X	4.77	2.72	0.57
Vehicle 1	4.27	4.01	0.94
Vehicle 2	4.08	3.96	0.97
Vehicle 3	5.92	6.69	1.13
Vehicle 4	6.84	7.11	1.04

Table 3 - Front/rear switching force comparison

While the front wiper switching force for vehicle X is comparable to that of the other vehicles, the rear wiper switching force is significantly lower. The ratio of rear to front switching force is 0.57 for vehicle X, compared to around 1 for the other vehicles. This raises the question of whether the problems with the vehicle X component arise from a design deficiency or manufacturing fault.

The results also give rise to an interesting ergonomic consideration. Given that the axes of movement (up/down, fore/aft) are orthogonal, at what angle from the up/down axis can a force be applied before the stalk will also switch in the fore/aft direction? The critical angle, i.e. the angle at which the switching load is applied in both axes is given by:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{F_{x,s}}{F_{y,s}} \right)$$

Where $F_{x,s}$, $F_{y,s}$ are the switching forces in the fore/aft and up/down axes, and θ is the angle from the up/down axis. For a rear/front switching ratio of 1, $\theta = 45^\circ$. For vehicle X however, the ratio of 0.57 gives a critical angle of 29.5° , meaning that a force applied at around 30° from the vertical axis would activate the rear wiper. Considering this from an ergonomic viewpoint, it is clear that the physical design of the column stalk may affect susceptibility to this problem. For example, the use of a rectangular cross-section would encourage switching forces to be applied to the flat edges of the stalk, hence in alignment with the axes of movement.

Comparison of measured characteristics with design specification

Table 4 shows the measured force values from vehicle X compared to the design specification agreed with the supplier. All of the switching forces measured are within specification, with the exception of the ‘intermittent’ position, i.e. the first ‘click’.

Function	Switching force / N		Min deviation / N	% of Nominal
	Specification	Measured		
Front wiper – intermittent	7.0 ± 2.0	4.81	-0.19	69%
Front wiper – 1 st speed	7.0 ± 2.0	5.20	+0.20	74%
Front wiper – 2 nd speed	7.0 ± 2.0	5.10	+0.10	73%
Rear wiper	4.0 ± 2.0	2.72	+0.72	68%

Table 4 - Comparison of measured values with design specification

Comparing the nominal switching force specification values for rear and front wiper operation shows a ratio of 0.57, equal to that measured for Vehicle X. Hence, assuming that the ‘best-case’ scenario from a manufacturing perspective is to produce a part which conforms to the nominal specification, the problem observed in the measured part is likely to remain, suggesting that the specifications were devised without understanding of the potential for usability issues to occur.

Analysis of the tolerances applied shows that the switching force can vary by $\pm 28\%$ of nominal for the front wiper and $\pm 50\%$ of nominal for the rear wiper while still within specification. In the ‘worst-case’ scenario (a rear switching force of 2.0N and front switching force of 9.0N), the rear/front force ratio is only 0.22, meaning that a force applied at just 12.4° from the vertical axis would activate the rear wiper. It is clear that the tolerances within the specification do not provide sufficient constraints to prevent the occurrence of feel quality and usability issues.

Comparison of measured characteristics with cross-vehicle specification

The measured values from vehicle X were compared to an existing cross-vehicle switch feel specification designed to ensure feel harmony across vehicles. It was found that all of the measured switching forces lie outside of the switch harmony specification, with the measured switching force of the rear wiper only 49% of the recommended value. The cross-vehicle specification was not adhered to during the design phase, suggesting either that it is not relevant to current design philosophy; or that it is unachievable by virtue of cost or technical constraint.

Discussion

Usability and specifications

Data from the measurements show significant differences between the column stalks from vehicle X and the comparison set – the most obvious being the lower switching force for the rear wiper. In all other cases, the up/down and fore/aft switching loads were relatively closely matched, i.e. a ratio of approximately 1. It is possible to evaluate this difference from an ergonomic perspective by calculating the angle at which an applied force will cause inadvertent operation – this may help to understand how the physical design of a column stalk interacts with its haptic characteristics to affect its usability. In order to fully understand the ergonomic elements of the issue however, it will be necessary to further investigate the mechanism of operation of column stalk functions from the driver’s perspective using customer trials; for example, there may be significant differences in the mode of operation of up/down and fore/aft functions which would be highlighted through observation. Incorporation of the force ratio into the design specification for the component would help to constrain the haptic characteristics of the different functions relative to each other, while an appropriately toleranced target for each function would ensure that the component does not exhibit excessive deviation from the nominal specification.

The appropriateness of specified tolerances falls under question in the case study above. The wide tolerance applied allows significant variations in force between functions, along with associated problems with usability, to occur while the component is still within specification. One explanation is that wide tolerances were applied in order to allow for ‘drift’ in an otherwise capable manufacturing process, whereby the deviation in part performance is small for a given batch but the mean performance varies over the longer term as a result of tool wear, for example. This explanation is supported by the fact that the force ratio for the measured part is the same as that for the nominal force specification, indicating that performance has shifted as a whole.

The study of interface usability is a well-established field, yet tends to focus on the efficiency with which a task can be completed; there is relatively little consideration to the affective, emotional elements of product interaction (Karat, 2003). Yet the sensory nature of interaction and its contribution to the perception of quality must not be ignored. The issues of specification discussed above raise an interesting question in this regard: how does the OEM ensure harmony of feel across the vehicle? It is not uncommon for switchpacks for a given vehicle to be produced by a number of different suppliers; if tolerances are not adequately specified, it would

be possible for two suppliers to produce parts with significantly different feel characteristics from the same specification. It is therefore vital to consider the emotional effect that engineering decisions will have on the customer.

Towards a model for feel quality

Wellings et al (2005) found that the understanding of feel quality is lacking throughout the automotive NPI process, with decisions being often based on the subjective opinions of the stakeholders making it difficult to communicate requirements further down the design chain. Even where specifications exist, it may not be possible to ensure that the product is aligned with customer preference due to a lack of both objective and subjective verification methodologies.

The assessment of feel quality is inherently subjective and as such poses a number of challenges for the engineer wishing to define a specification. The key element to engineering satisfaction into the product is the use of suitable customer-derived information upon which targets can be based, a problem which can itself be viewed as one of translation – moving information from the emotive language of the customer to the factual, data-driven world of the engineer. The means by which this information is derived must therefore be carefully selected to ensure its suitability.

Research conducted by the University of Warwick on the perception of switch-feel amongst customers of premium SUVs (Wellings et al, 2008) employed a combination of hedonic testing, semantic differential technique and content analysis of verbatim comments to build an understanding of the elements that influence the perception of switch-feel. The results showed clear preferences for switch feel across the vehicle set, albeit with bimodal responses for some vehicles. A principal component analysis (PCA) performed on the semantic differential data returned three factors accounting for 61% of the total variance of the data set, encompassing descriptors of both affective and physical characteristics of the product. Additional information was obtained from the content analysis of customer comments, including a correlation between switch size and preference.

The next stage of the problem is to create a model which links objective engineering data to the subjective, customer-derived information, thus allowing specifications to be based on actual customer preference and ensuring the relevance of design targets. In the switch size/preference case described above, preliminary design guidelines may be defined based on objective measurements of the switchpacks used in the study, subject to verification. Treatment of the

switch-feel semantic differential data is potentially more involved, given the number of variables in both the semantic data and objective metrics. Precedent for this approach exists within the automotive industry in the field of Sound Quality, where comparable methods have been used to model component and powertrain sound quality (Gallant et al, 2004; Lim 2001; Zhang, 1999).

While the acquisition of objective data can now be achieved through the Craftsmanship Haptics Laboratory, challenges remain in the identification of appropriate metrics to capture the key characteristics of the controls under test. These must reflect the content of the subjective factors such that predictions made by the model are accurate. Consideration must also be given to the limitations of the model; the subjective data employed must be relevant to the target market, and trends in preference which are likely to vary over time must be observed to maintain validity. Furthermore, products which polarise opinion, i.e. exhibit a bimodal distribution for measures of preference, may not be well suited to this modeling approach until the factors responsible for the bimodality are understood (Wellings et al, 2008).

Future work

Understanding how usability, sensory interaction and emotional impact shape the experience of the driver will aid the development of better user controls and interfaces. The 'HMI for Future Intelligent Vehicles' project at the University of Warwick Innovative Manufacturing Research Centre (WIMRC) aims to address issues of usability and satisfaction arising from the implementation of new automotive technologies, whilst retaining a human-centred approach. The methods developed through research into switch feel quality will form the basis for the project, enabling the investigation of customer wants and needs relating to HMI. The research will proceed to assess challenges and opportunities for the implementation of HMI in future vehicles, including the evaluation of new HMI technologies.

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